

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 3

 Acceptance of papers **MARCH, 2025**

Acceptance of papers
Published monthly

Topics
economics, technology, social sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli,
Head of the Department of Scientific
Research and Innovations, TSUE

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli – Senior
lecturer at TSUI

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL "INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY" HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **97-748-70-03**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: munis.iriskulova@gmail.com

Editorial board:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Cham Tat Huei,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Muhammad Imran Sadiq
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
Professor, Malaysia

Ahmed Aziz Ismail
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc),
Professor (Egypt)

Lee Chin
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
(Malaysia)

Asongu Simplicé
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
Cameroon

Rui Dang
Doctor of Chemistry (DSc), Professor, China

Zahoor Ahmed
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Turkey

Shujaat Abbas
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Russia

Tina A Coffelt
Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences
(PhD), USA

Judy B. Smetana
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), USA

CONTENTS

Increasing public awareness of financial products as a tool for ensuring economic growth	6
Gulnora Abdurakhmanova, Nazira Xodjaraxmanova	
Foreign experience in increasing the investment attractiveness of joint-stock companies through stock market instruments	13
Yulduzkhon Usmanova	
Integration of esg principles into the textile industry of uzbekistan: challenges and opportunities for sustainable development and attracting investment in the financial market.....	18
Ikramova Nodira Burkhon kizi	
Modern AI-powered chatbots: a comparative analysis of leading models	23
Ablakulova Shakhnoza Gayrat kizi, Ganiyev Ibragim Mamadiyevich	
The role of smart technologies in the development of recreational tourism	32
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
Analysis of energy intensity and factors affecting it in industrial enterprises.....	37
Dekhkanova Nargiza Sharifovna, Najmiddinov Yakhyo Fazliddin ugli	
Tendencies and scale of the shadow economy in uzbekistan.....	44
Koshanov Abdimurat Azat uli, Bazarbaeva Asiya	
Foreign experiences in regulating capital market activities	49
Sardor Ulmasovich	
Prospective ways of development of military manejeмент.....	56
Tulyaganova Shokhiya Gaffurovna	
Innovative management strategies in government support for agricultural enterprises: methodological foundations	62
Shaniyazova Zamira, Abdirazakova Asemay Jandulla Qizi	
Accounting for obligations related to securities issuance in enterprises: current procedures, challenges, and solutions.....	66
Umarova Shakhnoza Keldiyor kizi	
Case of mill's syndrome as a variant of atypical als in a central asian patient.....	71
Mavlanov Maruf Mexriddinovich, Rahimberdiyev Shoxruh Ravshanbekovich, Safarov Saydullo Ubaydullayevich	
The economics of renewable energy and its impact on economic growth.....	77
Razzokov Javokhir Nazirjon ugli, Dr. Siti Parhah	
Increasing organizational efficiency through strategic human resource management.....	82
Jurayeva Sarvinoz Baxtiyor kizi, Baymanova Mavlyuda Djurayevna	
Evolution of theoretical views on state regulation of the real sector of the economy	88
Isroilova Mukhabbat Rustamjon kizi	
Comparative characteristics of body composition in obesity phenotypes	94
Rano K.Dadabaeva, Elnora A.Abduganieva, Kenesh O.Djusupov, Indrani Kalkan, Oybek F.Eshmamatov	
Gastronomy and cuisine art	99
Xashimova Shaxnoza Shuxrat kizi	
Development of management competence in future pedagogical personnel	103
Jalolova Feruza Mirkamol kizi	
Promoting practical grammar as a subject.....	109
Elmirzayeva Maftuna Dusmurod kizi, Mustafoyeva Nigina Shuhrat kizi	
Opportunities for applying financial technologies as an educational tool to enhance the financial literacy of the population	112
Tukhtaeva Muyassar	

OPPORTUNITIES FOR APPLYING FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGIES AS AN EDUCATIONAL TOOL TO ENHANCE THE FINANCIAL LITERACY OF THE POPULATION

Tukhtaeva Muyassar

Doctoral student, Institute for the development of vocational Education

Abstract: The article analyzes the possibilities and directions of using financial technologies to improve financial literacy, which is an integral part of the population's economic competence. It also highlights the role of education in enhancing the financial literacy of the population. In particular, it discusses the importance of labor market analysis in ensuring the supply of qualified personnel to the modern labor market and describes its current demands for today's workforce.

Key words: financial technologies, financial literacy, online banking, financial services, financial inclusion.

INTRODUCTION

The education sector is undergoing significant changes, and financial technologies, known as “fintech,” are playing a decisive role in shaping the future of education. As traditional models of education evolve, innovative financial solutions are emerging to address challenges related to education financing. This intersection of finance and education not only makes education more accessible but also fundamentally transforms how people invest in education.

However, financial technologies are not only tools for improving education investment methods but also instruments for promoting financial education and meeting the principles of inclusivity and digitalization. Indeed, the impact of financial technologies on education goes beyond financing. As a result, these technologies also play a functional role in promoting financial literacy among students. Many fintech platforms offer students educational resources and tools aimed at understanding budgeting, saving, and responsible borrowing. In this regard, financial platforms are essential for developing students' competencies in learning and making informed, well-grounded decisions about their future financial well-being.

According to the World Economic Forum's Future of Jobs Report 2025, it is projected that by 2030, 39% of specialists' core skills will change [1]. Furthermore, an OECD international study on adult financial literacy conducted in 2023 revealed that only 53% of adults in participating countries met the basic threshold for financial literacy. Moreover, only 26% of respondents across 26 countries could correctly answer questions about simple and compound interest. These findings highlight the urgent need to enhance financial literacy and the demand for more transparent, enlightening financial solutions [2].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on the effectiveness of improving financial literacy by ensuring the integration of financial technologies into the education system was conducted, and results confirming the hypothesis were obtained. In particular, an inter-country study by Reem Ahmed AlSuwaidi showed a strong and positive relationship between financial literacy and the growth of the financial technology market, concluding that a high level of financial literacy of the population, measured through extended financial literacy training programs at all levels of education, can stimulate the expansion of the financial technology market [3]. The role of fintech in improving the financial literacy of the low-income population has been highly regarded due to the integration of financial

education and training programs into the provision of financial services, such as mobile banking or digital payments, at affordable and convenient prices.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is no secret that the weight of research results confirming the significant role of financial literacy in the social well-being of the population is increasing year by year. In recent years, the effective influence of financial literacy on a number of factors, such as making the right financial decisions, making informed financial choices, planning, and achieving overall financial efficiency, has become one of the topical subjects of scientific research due to the positive contribution of financial awareness to the quality of life of the population. Financial literacy is considered a structural component of economic competence, and education serves as a supporting force in its development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Today, due to the improvement and diversification of financial instruments and systems, it is necessary to establish continuous education including financial literacy to ensure a high quality of life in society. Constant reforms are being carried out in this direction on a global scale. Consequently, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has been cooperating with countries and regions, implementing projects to develop policies and mechanisms for financial consumer protection and financial literacy. For instance, the OECD established the International Network on Financial Education (INFE) to promote and facilitate international cooperation on financial literacy and education [4].

In Uzbekistan, the digital economy and digital financial services are actively developing. Within the framework of the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" strategy, great attention is being paid to the use of digital technologies and to increasing the digital literacy of the population. This plays a key role in creating the necessary environment for the population's adaptation to the digital world and in fostering a culture of using financial technologies [5].

At the same time, in the context of digitalization, financial literacy is essential for the effective use of digital financial services by the population, for ensuring financial security, and for active participation in the digital economy. The importance of improving financial literacy in Uzbekistan is reflected in the growing trend of people using fintech services. This trend is also driven by increased investment in the country's startup ecosystem. According to statistics, from 2022 to 2023, venture capital funds invested in local startups amounted to 7.1 million US dollars, 61 percent of which was directed toward fintech companies.

The continuous development of digital technologies forms a foundation for the supply of new types of goods and services to society, elevating the financial services industry to a new level. This also highlights the fact that every individual can be considered a potential victim of financial threats, as they are direct participants in the digital world and, often involuntarily, become users of financial technologies. This chain, formed within the digital world, underscores the importance of enhancing education aimed at improving individuals' financial literacy.

First of all, financial technologies refer to robo-advisors, mobile payments, investment applications, and online banking services, which have become standard at both international and local levels, creating high convenience and flexibility for users. Financial technology threats are defined as impulsive actions taken by individuals to purchase goods or services without justified need, often due to sudden behavioural or emotional changes triggered by external influences. Additionally, English scholars report that individuals familiar with financial principles rarely encounter difficulties in identifying various traps and deceptions. However, it is important to note that financial literacy is not merely the ability to conduct and manage monetary transactions; it is a multifaceted concept. Therefore, while financial literacy significantly contributes to recognizing fraud and avoiding deception, it should not be equated with simply managing daily income and expenses as a sufficient defense against risks arising from digitalization. The positive correlation between financial education and financial literacy highlights the urgency of promoting awareness, especially given the rapid increase in innovative technologies and their accessibility. Despite this growth, a significant portion of the population still lacks the skills to recognize reliable and secure financial technologies and make effective use of them. This underscores the role of education as the optimal solution.

Indeed, the definition provided by UNESCO aligns with this view: financial literacy is the possession of essential knowledge that enables individuals to identify, understand, and utilize the core functions of financial technologies. Uzbekistan's rising position in the Financial Technology Index reflects a rapidly evolving trend in the country. However, this progress stems from technological advancement, while the transformation of the population into active consumers of technology remains slow. A study conducted among the Chinese population confirmed the existence of an inverse relationship between age and

financial literacy. Although percentage figures may vary due to geo-economic differences, the general nature of this correlation is expected to remain consistent. In this context, the inclusive nature of financial technologies emerges as a viable solution. In today's highly competitive labor market, where adaptability and financial skills are key, traditional educational approaches to financial literacy are losing effectiveness. As the job market increasingly demands lifelong learning and strategic financial planning, financial technologies are emerging not only as tools for transactions but also as vital components of a dynamic educational ecosystem. They offer real-time, personalized data, simulations, and educational modules that facilitate the development of financial literacy a crucial skill in the 21st century.

Mobile banking applications enable users to track spending, set budgets, and monitor financial health in real-time. They serve as practical tools for learning budgeting and money management. Investment simulation platforms provide a risk-free environment to explore investment and portfolio management. Learners can experiment with various investment strategies and observe the outcomes without financial risk. Robo-advisors are automated platforms that offer financial advice and investment suggestions based on a user's income and expense patterns.

Picture 1. Online financial education platforms.

They help users understand complex financial concepts and make informed decisions. Online financial education platforms offer interactive courses, videos, and quizzes on a wide range of financial topics. Their flexibility and convenience make them an ideal choice for accessible financial education.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The integration of financial technologies in financial education not only overcomes the limitations of traditional teaching methods but also aligns with the demands of the modern digital economy. These technologies help create a more inclusive and accessible educational environment, serving as a tool to reach various segments of the population and equip them with essential financial management skills. Therefore, utilizing financial technologies in the following areas is crucial for enhancing the effectiveness of the educational process and preparing competitive professionals: it is necessary to develop specific indicators and methodologies for measuring and evaluating the effectiveness of FinTech education; increasing digital literacy among the population is important for the full use of FinTech opportunities; and by establishing cooperation between teachers, financial experts, and technologists in the creation of FinTech educational programs, it is possible to increase their competitiveness in the training of specialists for future professions, along with their financial literacy, which is a requirement of the times.

References:

1. World Economic Forum. (2025). The Future of Jobs Report 2025. World Economic Forum. Retrieved from: <https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-future-of-jobs-report-2025/>
2. OECD. (2023). OECD/INFE 2023 International Survey of Adult Financial Literacy. OECD Business and Finance Policy Papers, No. 39. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/56003a32-en>
3. Reem Ahmed AlSuwaidi, Charilaos Mertzanis. Financial Literacy and FinTech Market Growth Around the World. International Review of Financial Analysis, Volume 95, Part B, 2024, 103481. ISSN 1057-5219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2024.103481>
4. OECD. (2023). OECD/INFE 2023 International Survey of Adult Financial Literacy. OECD Business and Finance Policy Papers, No. 39. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/56003a32-en>
5. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni, 2020-10-05, PF-6079-son – "Raqamli O'zbekiston — 2030" strategiyasini tasdiqlash va uni samarali amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida. www.lex.uz/uz/docs/-5030957
6. U.I. Ergashev Ways to improve personnel policy in improving the quality of financial services provided by financial institutions. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15085137>
7. <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/journal/index.php/GED>

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2025. № 3

© When materials are reproduced, the INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

“The journal “INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY” has been registered by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 09.10.2024 under the registration number №390637. License number: C-5669633. PNFL: 30407832680027

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block,
House 17.

Acceptance of articles

Published every
monthly

Directions

Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

 Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

CERTIFICATE NUMBER: №390637

**ORDER NUMBER ACCORDING TO
THE LICENSE REGISTER: C-5669633**

CONTACT:

 Contact us
+998 97 748 70 03

 Telegram channel
t.me/scopus_IST2100

 Journal official website
<https://ist-journal.uz/index.php/IST>